

Talking the Talk: Interactive Oral Assessment to Promote Academic Integrity in Large Postgraduate Teacher Education Programmes

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Abstract

This paper explores the use of Interactive Oral (IO) assessment in a large postgraduate teacher education programme (>100) as a means to uphold academic integrity while enhancing student learning and engagement. Amidst the growing concern from the rapid emergence of generative AI tools, this paper suggests a well-designed Interactive Oral assessment for large class teaching and learning can offer a suitable alternative to traditional examinations and promote academic integrity among students. The paper addresses the importance of robust assessment design and the potential of Interactive Oral assessments to create inclusive, sustainable, and meaningful assessments for postgraduate learners. This paper draws from recent literature exploring Interactive Oral assessment and large class pedagogy and shares illuminating results from a recent student and staff evaluation at an Irish Higher Education Institution (HEI) to build the capacity of those who teach and support teaching and learning in Higher Education large classes.

Keywords: *Assessment; Academic integrity; Large class; Interactive Oral Assessment; Teacher education*

1. Introduction

The development of valid, reliable, and fair assessments is a continual challenge that has become more pronounced with the rise of free-to-use generative artificial intelligence large language models (e.g. ChatGPT, Sydney) and other online tools. Therefore, we must reconsider innovative forms of assessment that provide opportunities for authentic, meaningful ways for students to demonstrate learning. This paper examines the role of Interactive Oral Assessments as a useful innovation in large class teaching and learning, which may address these challenges while enhancing learning outcomes and maintaining the integrity of the academic process.

The emergence of generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) tools such as ChatGPT challenges the academic integrity of traditional higher education assessment (Concannon et al., 2023). In response to this challenge, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) need to develop awareness and understanding of generative AI tools and how to design assessments that preserve academic integrity while harnessing the opportunities to innovate assessments and harness the potential of AI tools for educational good (National Academic Integrity Network, 2023).

UNESCO's Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) Framework for 2030 is a pivotal initiative that aims to equip learners with essential knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes to tackle pressing global challenges like climate change, biodiversity loss, and inequality. The framework advocates embedding sustainable development principles in education to drive societal transformation. It emphasises holistic and interdisciplinary learning, critical thinking, values education, and participatory learning. Interactive Oral assessment, as an alternative strategy for evaluating learning, aligns with the UNESCO ESD framework so learners can enhance understanding, develop critical thinking, value reflection, and enhance engagement, thereby extending the cognitive, socio-emotional, and behavioural dimensions of learning (UNESCO, 2023).

This paper will describe how Interactive Oral assessment was designed for a large teacher education programme at an Irish Higher Education Institution. The author will discuss the findings of a student evaluation, emphasising the role of IO assessment in fostering a culture of academic integrity, enhancing student engagement, and aligning with broader educational goals. The paper will also address potential challenges and considerations for implementing this type of assessment in large classes.

2. Description of the Teaching and Learning Context

The teaching context involves a Postgraduate NFQ Level 9, ten ECTS modules with 115 learners, designed to provide foundational knowledge and skills for inclusive education to qualified, practising teachers across Primary, Post Primary and Further Education settings. The module content focuses on the historical development of special and inclusive education in Ireland, critical examination of related international and national frameworks, and exploration of key theories and literature. It aims to cultivate a reflective and critical approach to inclusion in education, examining learners' attitudes and the broader educational system's role in fostering inclusivity.

The module encompasses a variety of teaching strategies to address its comprehensive objectives, which include developing a critical understanding of disability and inclusive education concepts, examining relevant legislation and policies, and fostering critical reflection on attitudes toward inclusion. Over the last four years, students demonstrated their learning via a 4,000-word literature review, encouraging deep engagement with a chosen topic and developing critical inquiry skills. This review of relevant literature provides the opportunity to present critical inquiry and engagement with the assignment topic and relevant reading. The inquiry skills including interpretation, analysis, inference, and evaluation are reflected in a balanced and objective interrogation of relevant policy, research, and literature.

Over the last two academic years, we have observed a steady increase in support requests from students, namely concerning extension requests or delayed submissions. Despite a long lead-in time from assignment briefing to submission (4 months), we received extension requests from 25% of the large cohort who submitted an assignment. Additionally, large student numbers (100+) are accompanied by sizable marking loads (Jessop *et al.*, 2012), which necessitates reliance on many additional markers, including temporary marking staff, to support the assessment and administration of all assignments. For large student cohorts, decisions about assessment design involved managing resource limitations (such as financial cost, staff availability, turnaround time and related metrics). A further consideration concerns the challenges associated with marking consistency across large classes, using multiple assessors. Traditionally, module coordinators develop training programmes, pre-marking activities and lengthy consultation sessions to ensure agreement and understanding of grading strategies.

Interactive orals (IOs) offer a viable alternative to traditional assessment in large class teaching. They are a fair and reliable assessment method. IO aims to create a more dynamic and engaging evaluation environment, encouraging students to demonstrate their understanding in a professional, conversational setting. This shift intended to model

inclusive practices, reduce academic misconduct, and promote essential transversal skills like critical thinking and professional communication.

2.1. Interactive Oral Assessment

Designed within an evidence-based framework pioneered under the leadership of Danielle Logan-Flemming, Griffith University, IOs were first implemented at Dublin City University (DCU) in 2020 and successfully developed as a reliable form of assessment across the University in all disciplines (Ward *et al.* 2023). Research shows that IOs have the potential to develop many transversal skills, such as critical and creative thinking, professional communication, and personal agility (Tan *et al.*, 2021; Sotiriado, 2020).

An Interactive Oral Assessment (IO) is a two-way conversation using a professional scenario to stimulate a free-flowing discussion. It is designed to be a curious type of conversation where the assessors' prompts or questions allow students to showcase their learning in a professionally aligned environment. It facilitates the exploration of a student's deep and higher-order understanding of a topic. It is different from an oral exam or a viva where a question-and-answer format is used within strict exam conditions that can be sometimes stressful for the student.

IOs offer a viable alternative to traditional written assessment. Research indicates they are a fair and reliable assessment method (Sotiriadou *et al.*, 2020). Over the last three academic years, 11 DCU academics have used IO assessment across 15 different courses with 21 different cohorts. In total, almost 3,000 DCU students have experienced interactive oral assessment resulting in very positive feedback from assessors and students. Building on the success of IO and working with champions within DCU to develop a robust assessment mode intends to model inclusive practice, discourage academic misconduct and promote transversal skills (professional communication, collaboration, and critical thinking.)

Specially tailored for higher education and drawing inspiration from the International Baccalaureate curriculum, Interactive Oral Assessments (IOs) are authentic, spontaneous exchanges between a student and an evaluator, or among students themselves (Ward *et al.*, 2023). These assessments are rooted in constructivist theory, embracing andragogical strategies that emphasise active, contextualized learning. IOs serve to solidify knowledge in practical settings, thereby bolstering employability skills. They provide a genuine assessment experience, situated in a real-world or industry context, where students must articulate, synthesise, and apply their knowledge and skills orally.

2.2. Design Considerations for Interactive Oral Assessment

Insights gathered from Sotiriadou *et al.* (2019) research on Interactive Oral Assessments (IOs), along with support from a partnership with the research team from Griffith

University in Australia, DCU formed an interdisciplinary Interactive Oral Assessment community of practice (IO CoP), aimed at advancing and refining the implementation and design of IO practices among those who teach at the HEI. The engagement with Griffith University, particularly benefiting from the expertise of a seasoned practitioner and her colleagues, played a pivotal role in the CoP's achievements. Members of this community brought a variety of approaches to the table, fostering a mutually beneficial learning environment and enhancing the collective expertise in IO practices.

Many of the challenges of implementing Interactive Oral assessments relate to scheduling and perceived time of marking, particularly in large classes. However, oral assessments are scalable, and these concerns can be remedied with careful design, and planning, including collaboration among staff in a programme when possible.

An additional challenge for many students and assessors is their relative inexperience with this type of assessment, which could lead to anxiety. Therefore, scaffolding the assessment and giving students practice in explaining their understanding during the learning process is vital (Theobald, 2021).

Figure 1.0: Interactive Oral Assessment as Authentic Assessment Design. (Sotiriadou et al., 2020)

Drawn from the work of Sotiriadou *et al.* (2020), Figure 1.0 illustrates the key objectives and characteristics of effective IO assessment design, which are further explored below:

- **Alignment with Learning Outcomes:** Align the assessment task with the module and/or Programme Learning Outcomes to ensure coherence in learning objectives.
- **Contextualisation and Authenticity:** Craft the assessment to be authentic. Instead of hypothetical questions, have students assume roles or personas to navigate real-life scenarios.
- **Duration of Assessment:** Determine the optimal length, balancing sufficient time for students to demonstrate learning without causing fatigue. A 10–20-minute duration is recommended.
- **Marking Rubric:** Develop a marking rubric corresponding to the Course Learning Outcomes (CLOs) to guide consistent and objective evaluation.
- **Procedures and Protocols:** Establish clear procedures for conducting assessments. Develop a varied question/scenario bank to ensure equivalency in challenge and alignment with CLOs, drawing on effective prompting techniques.

Scaffolding

- **Preparation:** Ensure students understand the assessment's purpose, structure, and success criteria early in the module timeline.
- **Practice Opportunities:** Integrate practice sessions within the curriculum, such as peer-to-peer exercises, and provide exemplars with feedback to model expected performance.
- **Communication Enhancement:** Foster communication skills within the classroom to reduce assessment anxiety and build confidence.

Scheduling

- **Time Management:** Allocate adequate time for both the Interactive Oral Assessment and subsequent marking within each time slot. Allowing for some spillage in case of unforeseen technical issues.
- **Logistics for Large Cohorts:** Utilise digital scheduling tools for managing numerous appointments. Distribute allocations among assessors, ensuring they are well-versed in the assessment's protocols and rubrics.

Implementation

- **Equitability:** Maintain fairness by involving multiple assessors in conducting and evaluating the assessments, guided by the established rubric.
- **Record Keeping:** Record interviews for moderation purposes and to resolve any grade disputes.

- Supportive Environment: Create a relaxed atmosphere using conversational techniques to minimise student stress and enable optimal performance.

3. Student Evaluation Results

A comprehensive evaluation of the assessment experience, as voiced by students who engaged with IO, offers insightful reflections on its effectiveness, appeal, and pedagogical value within large postgraduate teacher education programmes. This evaluation highlights the strengths and areas for enhancement in the IO approach and underscores its impact on student engagement, understanding, and overall learning experience. Through a detailed analysis of feedback on various aspects of the IO, ranging from preparation and support to the inclusivity of the pedagogy, this section will offer some insights into how the IO resonates with students' learning preferences and aligns with the programme's objectives. Additionally, it will explore suggestions for refining the assessment process, ensuring that it fosters a meaningful and supportive learning environment for all participants.

Most students (85% of 123 respondents) rated their overall satisfaction with the Interactive Oral Assessment positively. Notably, 103 respondents awarded high scores, indicating a strong appreciation for this assessment method. Students found various supports and resources valuable in their preparation for the assessment. The sample interactive oral video was highlighted as useful and received high usefulness ratings from most respondents.

Eighty-six (70% of respondents) students felt that the Interactive Oral Assessment effectively facilitated a deeper understanding of the module content, with several respondents specifically mentioning the practical nature of the assessment in enhancing their learning. When asked about the appeal of the assessment, students appreciated its practicality and interactive nature. Comments highlighted the benefit of engaging in a realistic, conversational format that differs from traditional written assessments.

Respondents acknowledged the Interactive Oral Assessment's role in supporting inclusive pedagogy. The assessment was seen as beneficial for a diverse range of learners, including those who excel in verbal communication and those who appreciate practical, real-world learning contexts.

While overall feedback was positive, some students suggested enhancements such as more specific scenarios and additional preparatory resources to further support diverse learning needs. Notably, most students expressed gratitude for the supportive environment and the unique assessment experience. The practical nature of the assessment and the opportunity to engage in a meaningful conversation were frequently praised. Some students recommended narrowing the focus of the assessment scenarios and providing more detailed preparatory materials to enhance clarity and relevance.

Overall, Interactive Oral Assessment was well-received by students, who found it to be an effective, engaging, and inclusive method of demonstrating skills and knowledge. While there are areas for improvement, particularly in terms of scenario focus and additional support resources, the assessment overall was viewed as a positive and beneficial component of this large postgraduate teacher education module. Future iterations of the assessment will benefit from incorporating student feedback to further refine and enhance its effectiveness and inclusivity.

4. Challenges and Implementation Considerations for Large Classes

Reflecting on implementing IO as a fair and reliable assessment method provides a nuanced understanding of practical implications and the pathways for optimising its effectiveness in large class settings. Several challenges and strategic responses have been considered and can be shared with fellow educators to build capacity sustainably. These include:

Resource Intensity: Implementing IOs in large classes necessitates a substantial investment in staff and material resources. The requirement for several trained assessors and the logistical demands of coordinating such assessments are significant. Institutions may consider developing communities of practice (CoP) to allow for the sharing of expertise, the development and sharing of materials, and the provision of opportunities for discussion, which offers invaluable support. Tangible examples of this support were evident in the DCU CoP through collaborative designs that were constructively aligned, scaffolded assessment strategies that had an integrated IO component, scenario planning, and the development of rubrics and prompts for the IOs. CoP members helped their colleagues create examples of recorded IOs for each pilot, which were captured during the weekly CoP meetings.

Consistency: The integrity of IOs hinges on the standardisation of assessment protocols. To this end, developing comprehensive assessor training strategies and robust assessment rubrics is vital. These measures ensure that despite the scale of implementation, every student's work is evaluated against a consistent set of criteria, thereby upholding fairness and reliability.

Technology Dependence: While technology can streamline the administration of IOs in large classes, it also introduces potential pitfalls, such as technical malfunctions and issues of digital access and literacy. Institutions should invest in reliable technology platforms and provide adequate technical support and training for assessors and students. Furthermore, contingency plans should be in place to address any technological disruptions during the assessment process.

Student Anxiety: IO, as an innovative assessment approach, can be intimidating, possibly impacting students' performance. To alleviate this, educators can employ various strategies such as conducting mock assessments, offering clear and detailed guidelines on what is expected, and establishing robust support systems. These approaches can help demystify the assessment process for students, reducing anxiety and enabling them to showcase their true capabilities.

The thoughtful integration of IOs in large class settings necessitates a strategic approach that balances resource scalability with the maintenance of assessment quality and student support. By addressing the identified challenges, institutions can leverage IOs to foster academic integrity, enhance student engagement, and promote deeper learning in large classes.

5. Conclusion

The paper reiterates the impact of Interactive Oral assessments in the contemporary educational landscape, particularly in large postgraduate teacher education programmes. The author contends that they have the potential to uphold academic integrity, enhance student learning and engagement, and contribute to sustainable educational practices. Arguably beyond teacher education, the benefits observed in terms of authenticity of assessment could potentially be relevant to the assessment of large cohorts in postgraduate professional learning programmes in other disciplines.

Findings from student evaluation at DCU support the emergent literature on IOs. They reveal the effectiveness of IOs in enhancing student engagement and learning. Overall, students who participated in IOs demonstrated a deeper understanding of the subject matter and favoured IO as a viable approach to assessment.

Most students found IOs more engaging than traditional assessments, citing the interactive and conversational nature of the assessment as critical factors. Students reported a better grasp of the course material, attributing this to the active learning aspect of IOs, which required them to articulate their thoughts and respond to immediate prompts from an assessor.

This paper synthesises the evaluation findings and emerging literature on Interactive Oral assessments' role in fostering a culture of academic integrity, enhancing student engagement, and aligning with broader educational goals. It also addresses potential challenges and considerations for implementing these assessments in large classes.

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